

SOCIAL NETWORKS

SOCIAL NETWORKS AS SIGNIFICANT FACTOR IN THE PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN KOSOVO

ARLINDA BEKA

Faculty of Education, University of Prishtina,
Republic of Kosovo

KEYWORDS: Facebook, information, education, LinkedIn

ABSTRACT: Professional development is a continuous trend of youth in Kosovo. The tendency of the students and other youth to reach relevant information, which affects their professional, pushes them to refer to various sources of information.

So far the main sources of information are considered local newspapers, television advertisements and newsletters that have been displayed in different locations. Now these information platforms are considered inappropriate by the youth. They prefer more to use the social networks where they can access information. Social networks that are mostly used among the youth of our country are considered Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn. This paper presents data on how students of the University of Prishtina regular use social networks.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.15208/pieb.2014.17>

Vol.14 (3), PP.147-151

Source: Beka A., 2014. "Social networks as significant factor in the professional development of young people in Kosovo", *Perspectives of Innovations, Economics & Business*, Vol.14(3), pp.147-151, <http://dx.doi.org/10.15208/pieb.2014.17>

Literature review

Technology is among the most important tools in the development of modern societies. The use of technology is one of the necessary skills that individual must have. This has become inseparable part of our everyday life. With introducing of new era of technology like smart phones, tablets and other digital media, our lives, our communication and networking with one another have changed dramatically.

Certainly the developments in technology have influenced the education field as well, particularly in teaching and learning. Easy access to information which is available in modern world is a privilege that past societies lacked. Today with the technology development and globalization impact people from all over the world have access to information almost in real time.

Even though the technology and the new media is widely used among all kinds of people and in all kinds of activities there have been written many articles by different scholars which have given many reasons that the use of technology has largely negative outcomes, especially to the development of young children. On the other hand still it is argued that society's approach to information published in different sites can help them getting quick and useful information for their professional development and beyond. In some form use of technology has become part of the culture for different societies in the world. For this reason many countries have included in school curricula, the use of information technology and internet access.

If we refer to numerous publications on this matter we will see the importance of using technology in the education of children and youth professional development. As

- 147 -

almost all of us agree that the computer technologies and the new media have become an unavoidable part of our daily life, there are scholars that consider this to be important to our teaching and learning opportunities too. Therefore computer technologies have become one of the most influential pedagogical tools in the classroom (Oblinge and Rush, 1997) and their impact on learning has been profound (Mitra, 2000).

Integrating technology into the curriculum of the classroom is becoming an inseparable part of good teaching. The use of technology should foster learning that goes beyond information retrieval to problem solving and should promote the deep processing of ideas, increase student engagement with the subject matter, promote teacher and student motivation for learning, and increase student-to-student and student-to-teacher interactions (Mills, 2006). He/she becomes first of all a learner as he/she needs to be in line with the contemporary trends of technology. In such environment teachers shift from teaching their students to learning with their students and sometimes learning from their students (McCain, T. and Jukes, 2001).

The teacher becomes instructional designer, instructional facilitator, coach, evaluator and technologist (Mills, 2006).

Contemporary idea that all young people can be regarded as 'digital natives' (Prensky, 2001) highly adapting to digital technologies by virtue of their lifelong exposure to them has captured the academic and popular imagination (Barnes, Marateo, and Pixy Ferris, 2007). Though the idea emerged almost a decade ago, only recently it has drawn attention from researchers. This emerging body of work has so far been helpful in dispelling the myth of homogenous generations of 'tech-savvy' young people and in demonstrating the persistence of significant digital divides within populations (Salaway and Caruso, 2007)

If education is viewed as a system for preparing young people to make a valuable contribution to our society in adult life, quality may be seen in terms of the cost-effective use of teacher time and resources and the functional effectiveness of school-leavers in the job market. However, if the aims of education are seen in terms of fostering individual achievement and maximizing human potential, quality may be seen in terms of the intrinsic value of educational experiences and the individual achievements and personal fulfillment of school-leavers (Davis, Desforges, Jessel, Somekh, and Taylor, 2005).

Information technology tools can be embedded within each other and used in conjunction with other tools and materials in a number of subject disciplines. For example, number is a tool that may be used within mathematics which in turn is used when analyzing scientific data, providing access to scientific thinking to those who have difficulty with mathematics (Davis et al., 2005).

In discussion of contemporary IT tools we shall take four areas of IT capabilities which are widely used nowadays (Davis et al., 2005): communicating ideas and information, handling information, modeling, and measurement and control. At a more sophisticated level, a word processor permits the writer to rework the text without having to 'remember' it as a whole, cut and paste many pieces of paper or rewrite manually. For some, a change in the way text is presented increases its value and provides some 'mental distance' from its production, both of which encourages critical rewriting (Davis et al., 2005).

Collaborative groups of authors can share a screen more easily than a book and the ease of changing or recovering writing increases risk taking. Teachers can organize collaborative writing with a word processor to encourage children to engage in critical review of each other's work (Graves, 198). Information technology provides a range of information-handling tools which can help to alleviate this problem (Davis et al., 2005).

Computer modeling also provides support in learning to handle abstract concepts, for example in science. Also according to the authors information technology can also permit learners to take many more accurate measurements and so engage in creative exploration of a phenomenon, taking into account more factors than would otherwise have been possible (Davis et al., 2005).

Today, young people demonstrate in a variety of tasks, projects, and programs that they have the cognitive and social abilities to use new multimedia and network centric technologies optimally and with self-efficacy (Bandura, 1997). Youth have developed mental models for using technology at school, home, and work by becoming totally immersed in computer network environments. Young people seem to have the ability to define, create, and update their own mental model on the use of technology with minimal support from traditional event-oriented courseware.

The newest trend in using of the technology in education is the use of the social media or how is called in now days the New Media. Their impact in our daily life is increasing, and educative institutions particularly of the higher education are trying to get the effective use of them. Today almost all relevant educative institutions have an official page/account in one or more of the new media tools: i.e. Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube or others. They use them as a channel to transmit their information or to gather feedback from recipients, and they found this very useful and easy way.

Kosovo even though a small and developing country has been influenced by new trends of social media. Having a quit young population with average age of 28 Kosovo's population is very active in social networks and usage of new media for work, study or just for fun. This is true particularly for the urban areas. Students are using social media to share and exchange information among themselves as well as to stay connected.

Methodology

The goal of this research to study the frequency of use of the social networks among the youth/students and for what purpose they use it. Also the focus of this research was whether the usage of the social media from students influence their professional development.

Research was conducted with 97 students of bachelor and master level of studies. Participants in this research where students from 8 different faculties of the University of Prishtina, coming from different parts of our country. Sample selection is done through probability-based technique.

The methodology is quantitative. Measuring instruments are used with sufficient test items to cover this issue. Questionnaire was designed with different variations of questions, including dichotomous questions, the selection of answers options and questions have been built according Likert scale.

The scale of measurement of the instrument is nominal, ordinal, interval and ratio. The research data are processed through Statistical Package for the Social Science - SPSS.

Outcomes results

The data which were obtained through this research shows that students in the University of Pristina are regular users of different social networks. Almost every one of them has more than one account on different pages. Social Network which is used mostly by students is Facebook, where 96.9% have account on this site. The second most used network in our country is Instagram where 41.2% of students have

account, Twitter is the third most usable network by students with a total of 36.1% to 29.9%, and LinkedIn network ranks as the fourth usable by students of the University.

STATISTICS

		Do you use any of this social networks	Facebook	Twiter	Instagram	Linkedin
N	Valid	97	94	35	40	29
	Missing	0	3	62	57	68

Apart from their personal account, these students are part of group networks in these pages, which they have created for their group of studies. Almost every one of the respondents is part of these groups. Those pages seem to serve them to get various information that are of some interest to them. 84.5% of respondents said that they were part of the group pages that are open at their study groups, while 15.5% are not yet interested to be part of these groups and are mainly students of the first years.

DO YOU HAVE A SOCIAL NETWORKING PAGE, WHICH BELONGS TO THE GROUP?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	82	84.5	84.5	84.5
	No	13	13.4	13.4	97.9
	I don't know	2	2.1	2.1	100.0
	Total	97	100.0	100.0	

Respondents answered on what purpose they use these networks. 90.7%% said that they use social networks for getting and distributing various information, which can be useful to them in their professional development. While, on the other hand, 8.2% of them use it for more fun.

FOR WHAT YOU USE MOSTLY THIS PAGE OF YOUR GROUP?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Valid	Getting information	81	83.5	84.4	84.4
	Because of pictures	1	1.0	1.0	85.4
	For entertainment	7	7.2	7.3	92.7
	Distribution of materials that helps our professional development	7	7.2	7.3	100.0
	Total	96	99.0	100.0	
Missing	System	1	1.0		
Total		97	100.0		

And in the last question, what have been the benefits in your professional field of studies, students have had more than one benefit from the information that they have received from these social networks. Respondents answered as follows: 29.9% have received various trainings, which have helped their professional growth; 19.6% have benefited through social networks to participate in various workshops; 13.5% have received possibilities to be part of summer schools within and outside the country; 28.8% of them have received the opportunity to pursue internship in various local institutions; while 8.2% said they had not benefited anything.

Conclusion

From our observation we can conclude that students are regular users of social networks. Technology for them is of great importance due to quick and easy access to information which helps their professional development.

Within all departments and faculties of the University students have created special pages in social networks; this helps them to receive and disseminate information. This form not only gives students the opportunity to receive information very quickly, but also saves their time and their finances.

Besides information, students through social networks are beneficiaries of various activities, such as training, workshops, summer schools or internships. In order to follow the trend for their professional development, students become linked to a more than one group pages in social networks. Contact with their peers, although virtually, enables them to cooperate and help each other by sharing information and instructions.

References

- Bandura, A., 1997. *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. New York: W. H. Freeman
- Barnes, K., Marateo, R., and Pixy Ferris, S., 2007. *Teaching and learning with the Net Generation*. Retrieved May 5, 3(4). Retrieved May 5, 2014m <http://innovateonline.info/index.php?view=>
- Graves, D., 1989. *Writing: Teachers and children at work*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.
- McCain, T. and Jukes, I., 2001. *Windows on the future: Education in the age of technology*, California: Thousand oaks. Corwin Press
- Mills, S. C., 2006. *Using the internet for active teaching and learning*. USA: Pearson Education
- Mitra, A., 2000. "Introduction to special issue," *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, Vol.23(1), 1-3, <http://dx.doi.org/10.2190/FC2G-TCUV-XKW8-W32G>
- Davis, N., Desforjes, Ch., Jessel, J., Somekh, B., Taylor, C., 2005. *Using information technology effectively in teaching and learning*, Chap 1: *Can quality in learning be enhanced through the use of IT* (N. D. Bridget Somekh, Ed.) London, UK: Taylor & Francis e-Library
- Oblinge, D. and Rush, S. (Eds.), 1997. *The learning revolution*, Bolton, MA: Anker Publishing Company, Inc.
- Prensky, M., 2001. "Digital natives, digital immigrants", *On the Horizon*, Vol.9(5), 1-6, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/10748120110424816>
- Salaway, G. and Caruso, J., 2007. *ECAR study of undergraduate students and information technology*, Boulder, CO: EDUCAUSE Center for Applied Research